

PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION METHODS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF BUSINESS FUNCTIONS AND FORMS

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Abstract: This article reveals the content of effective organization and management of methodological work in preschool educational organizations, the opinions of foreign scientists on methodological work, the subjects of methodological work.

Key words: Methodical work, methodical work management, system, pedagogue, methodical supply, management, modernization, innovation.

Pre-school education, the organization of the work of methodical content and the development of professional skills of caregivers of their activities with features that are aimed at improving the quality complete. Agree to this methods that reflect the activities of the service differs from the content of the following functions:

- his personal qualities and professional skills development of teachers, the teachers in this regard resistant to stress in the development of their business activities to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical communication methods accounted for the choice of teachers of professional activity of creative pedagogical skills and increase encouragement the citizens of recommendations development;

- teachers of the world of scientific-research activities to participate in creative activity of encouragement development;

- update the educational process and pre-school education institutions of education with other systems o'zaro development cooperation, teaching experience o'in the educational process to the basics of development, psychology, pedagogy, and teachers of preschool educational institutions of the sciences logoped the scientific achievements of the system used teachers from experience are the work of use.

Pre-school education generally its is built based on the structure of the system we work on the following activities:

- preschool education institutions of the educational process of exercising forecasting and goal setting;

- education is the process of exercising and planning;

- preschool education institutions of the educational process of the

implementation of the organization;

- preschool education education is the process of exercising with encouragement;
- preschool education institutions of the educational process, the implementation of the correction.

Yu.K.Babanskiys methodical work combined with the overall goals of education organization's "copyright" model and educate children who strive to create modern scientific studies in teaching experience or present to the formation of the team is directed.

Organized in the form of methodical work in the first place, you need to consider the following: for most first of all, the complexity of the task and goal of the year, pre-school education organization located specific conditions worthy of diversity.

Methods of organization form a two - *team and individual* a separate group is desirable to rsat. One of the first scientific-practical conferences, methodical associations of teachers creative pre-school education, the organization's methods cabinets and skills training of the world includes. A man had two sons two - training, individual tips, coaching, personal theme to work in a creative, individual includes.

Methodical maintenance and professional management of the work is a part of teachers' activities, their distinct features is.

Innovative methods are generally in the organization of the supply with the following opportunities:

- the mode of development of the organization to ensure the performance in educationis justified;
- mto select the content of its work, we, the teachers, the development of self , the possibility of;
- teachers, innovative methods about information to give, and the examination of the organization;
- of teachers' professionaland pedagogical activity of the methods with armed to personal development towards effective effects shows;
- education services quality and the level of the increase;
- education in the market of salaries of competitiveness level;
- education is the process of methodical and scientific-methodical provision;
- educationm the process of information-didactic to provide.

Methodical work quality education a significant effect on the efficiency of

effective can be.

References:

1. Olimov S. A. THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS MAIN DIRECTIONS AND LEVELS OF ORGANIZATION OF METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT // " CANADA" INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DEVELOPMENTS IN EDUCATION, SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES. – 2023. – T. 9. – №. 1.
2. Olimov S. A. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida innovatsion inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etish // Science and Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 4. – С. 953-958.
3. Alimov, A., Turgunov, A., Chorshanbiev, Z., Jamolov, A., & Olimov, S. (2022, November). Creation of distance learning software for assessing the learning outcomes of future engineers based on the "smart" technology. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2647, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
4. Olimov Sodiq Anvar o'g'li. (2024). Scientific-Methodological Foundations Of Organization And Management Of Methodical Work In Pre-School Educational Organizations. Genius Repository, 28, 54–58. Retrieved from <https://geniusrepo.net/index.php/1/article/view/575>
5. Бегимкулов, У. Ш., & Олимов, С. А. (2024). Информационнокоммуникационные технологии организации и управления инновационным методическим обеспечением в дошкольных образовательных организациях. Информатика. Экономика. Управление - Informatics. Economics. Management, 3(1), 0159–0168. <https://doi.org/10.47813/2782-5280-2024-3-1-0159-0168>
6. Murodova Farangis G'anisherovna. (2024). Effective methods of forming children's speech competence through riddles and quick sayings in preschool educational organizations. Genius Repository, 28, 47–51. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusrepo.net/index.php/1/article/view/530>
7. Sayfullayeva, D., & Sharobiddinova, G. (2023). BO 'LAJAK TEXNOLOGIYA FANI O 'QITUVCHILARINI KREATIVLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUNI. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(11), 48-51.
8. Sayfullayeva DA. Methodology of using autocad software in developing technical creativity of students. GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) № 10.2022. B-661-671;.

